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Enhanced Detection and Segmentation of Retinal Exudates in Diabetic Retinopathy using a Feature Pyramid Network with EfficientNet-B0 Encoder

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Abstract

Objective: To investigate the Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) application using a Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) with the use of EfficientNet-B0 as an encoder for exudates detection and segmentation in retinal images and also the performance of precise exudates evaluation. **Methods:** The two-stage method mainly detects and eliminates the optic disc, which is subsequently essential to nullifying false positives, and then detects the segment exudates. The model is based on the EfficientNet-B0 encoder in the FPN architecture, which benefits from multi-scale feature representation, which is fundamental in exudates of dissimilar sizes and shapes. The DiaRetDB1-V2.1 public dataset⁽¹⁾ is considered to evaluate the proposed model. The dataset consists of 89 color fundus images and was split into 7:3, which indicates that 70% of the data was utilized for training and 30% for testing. To validate the proposed model, the Test Pixel Accuracy and Mean IoU are the performance metrics, and these values are compared with the state-of-the-art models. **Findings:** This study introduced an innovative method for finding the segment exudates in retinal images using an FPN with EfficientNet-B0 as an encoder. The proposed approach consists of two key parts: the first is to find the optical disc in retinal images and remove it. The second is to identify and perform accurate segmentation of the exudates. The FPN with EfficientNet-B0 achieved the highest pixel accuracy of 99.80%, which indicates that the accurate classified pixels were higher than the other models. Test Set mIoU provided the overlap measure in performance with the ground truth. A higher value of mIoU indicates better performance in terms of precision and recall. The proposed FPN with EfficientNet-B0 achieved mIoU by 81.52% which is better than Unet, UnetPlusPlus and MANet methods. **Novelty:** The proposed research discovered a powerful and effective method for segmenting and detecting exudates in retinal images using the FPN EfficientNet-B0 Encoder.

Keywords: Diabetic Retinopathy; Exudates Detection and Segmentation; FPN; EfficientNetB0; Optic Disc Detection and Segmentation

1 Introduction

Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) often referred to as exudative maculopathy, is a severe and dangerous complication of diabetes wherein it affects the eyes. The retina is responsible for vision; thus, the diseased state may cause unnoticed all the way to the point of affecting vision in patients at high risk. The most unique characteristic of diabetic retinopathy is the presence of exudates. They are lipid and protein infiltrations that grow out of damaged blood vessels in the retina, which continue to grow at an alarming rate. These accumulations are responsible for monitoring disease progression and, if not properly addressed; may expose the patient to more impaired vision.

Despite the lack of symptoms in the early stages of diabetic retinopathy, the vision will worsen. The other signs that point to the development of this condition are blurry vision, colors appearing dull or washed out, and floaters or dark strings floating in the patient's field of vision. Hard exudates, which can be observed in the eye examination, are even more troubling, as they indicate extensive retinal leakage and a more serious risk of vision loss. The exudates' management in diabetic retinopathy is based on tight control of blood sugar, blood pressure, and lipid levels to reduce the rate of progression. Exudate detection and segmentation require high-end imaging technologies and sophisticated algorithms. Researchers usually use fundus photography, fluorescein angiography, and optical coherence tomography to acquire high-quality images of the retina. Thereafter, scientists apply computational methods ranging from conventional image processing to advanced artificial intelligence techniques to analyze them⁽²⁾.

In particular, Machine Learning (ML) models, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have demonstrated the ability to obtain a high accuracy of automatic retinal picture analysis. In these challenges, such as image quality, motion blur, poor illumination, or patient characteristics, medical images obtained for exudate detection can significantly differ in replicability, which impacts the effectiveness of diagnostic and monitoring systems. Some of the things that make exudates more challenging in terms of identification include their likeness with drusen, cotton wool spots, and reflections from the nerve fiber layers⁽³⁾.

Although fundus photography is the most common modality, merging disparate data types, such as fluorescein angiography or optical coherence tomography, leads to a more accurate view of the state of the retina algorithm performance varies among different ethnic groups and demographics, it may require a vast amount of testing or even require algorithmic adjustments for various demographics⁽⁴⁾. All these challenges highlight the crucial need and role played by continued research and development in the sectors of medical imaging and artificial intelligence. Overcoming these challenges successfully will increase the ability of health systems to diagnose and treat DR and ultimately reduce vision loss in the diabetic population.

Cheng Wan, Yingsi Chen, Han Li, Bo Zheng, Nan Chen, Weihua Yang⁽⁵⁾, proposed a novel encoder-decoder with an attention-based EAD-net for lesion segmentation. By far the final work on DR is an approach with a Convolutional neural network containing three main parts: encoder module, attention module, and decoder modules named the EAD-Net. The novel module EAD-Net for clinical diagnosis of DR showed effective work to segment four types of lesions. This successful segmentation is highly valuable for clinical usage to observe and diagnose. The Aruna Priya Latha⁽⁶⁾ presented novel classification and segmentation methods in DR image analysis for more accurate results. The encouraged methodology consists of four stages: preprocessing, DR classification, exudates segmentation, and performance assessment. The original RGB retinal photographs are broken into three channels during preprocessing: the

R-Assignment, the G-Graph, and the B-Graph. Afterward, each channel is threefold amplified. These amplified pictures are then fed into a Hybrid Centric CNNs classifier, which distinguishes them into Grade 0 and Grade 1. After classifying them, a distinctive way to segment exudate lesions was utilized to further identify the existence of exudates in DR images.

A comparative analysis of various deep Convolutional neural network architectures for minimizing parameters of a residual CNN with residual skip connections was provided in the paper⁽⁷⁾. The network was used to carry out semantic segmentation of exudates in retinal images. An appropriate image augmentation technique was used to boost the VGG-19 network architecture. A modernized capsule network was presented in the research work⁽⁸⁾ for diabetes retinopathy detection and classification. Convolution and the primary capsule layers are responsible for rendering the features from the fundus image, while the class capsule layer and softmax thinking are used to capture how likely the image falls into a class. For evaluation, the four-performance metrics are gathered from the Messidor dataset. A novel DR screening method⁽⁹⁾ was introduced in the literature by applying deep learning asymmetry features and asymmetric deep learning feature extraction. In the study done by Yinghua Fu, Ge Zhang a, Xin Lu a, Honghan Wu b, Dawei Zhang⁽¹⁰⁾, a novel neural network named RMCA (Residual Multi-scale feature fusion Channel Attention) U-net was proposed for hard exudates segmentation in fundus images. The network adopts U-shaped architecture and combines the residual structure to grasp the little cue of hard exudates. The performance indicated that the well achieved than traditional U-net.

Existing research methodologies for diabetic retinopathy (DR) image analysis are also limited by several gaps. While⁽⁴⁾ has shown the success of the EAD-Net for lesion segmentation, its generalizability to varying datasets and resilience against different levels of image qualities are unexplored areas. Aruna Priya Latha et al.⁽⁵⁾ proposed an extensive DR classification and segmentation, this successfully met the experimental requirements except for the scalability of the Hybrid Centric CNNs classifier on larger datasets as well as adaption to other retinal diseases. The research work⁽⁶⁻⁸⁾ which performed comparative analysis minimizing parameters for exudate segmentation, also avoided the impact of different augmentation techniques on a number of network architectures. However, the capsule network for DR detection and deep learning asymmetry features have not been verified on diverse datasets or complex image transformations. The RMCA U-net⁽¹⁰⁾ was proposed for segmenting hard exudates, however, its adaptability to other lesion types and ability under variable image qualities were not investigated. Moreover, the computational efficiency and practical utility of these sophisticated methodologies for real-time clinical use especially in resource-limited settings needs validation. To overcome these drawbacks, the following steps need to be taken. A detailed comparative analysis of the existing methods needs to be done through implementation. The implementation of the existing models gives us a thorough understanding of the drawbacks that are present in those models. This process will be followed for both the methods of DR classification and segmentation. Once the drawbacks are identified tailored deep planning models need to be created to overcome these drawbacks. Addressing the weakness specifically the resultant proposed model will achieve better results when compared to the existing models.

2 Methodology

This study started with a new method for detecting and segmenting exudates in retinal images using a Feature Pyramid Network with EfficientNet-B0 as an encoder. The proposed approach consists of two key parts: (i) To find the optical disc in retinal images and remove it. (ii) To identify and perform accurate segmentation of the exudates. The optical disc, the bright, disk-shaped area in the retina where the optic nerve enters the eye, is often radiantly displayed in images of the retina. It was removed as its high intensity and contrast make it appear conjointly with the exudates, resulting in false positives during subsequent analysis. To achieve it, the method first uses an FPN architecture with the EfficientNet-B0 encoder to model the initial spatial hierarchies of the retina images. The FPN obtains contextual information in a variety of areas, which is vital to determining the distinction between the optic disc and other parts of the retina. Once the optic disc is visually identified, a morphological shift-based transforming technique is used to isolate the optic disc, followed by removing it from the analysis. This pre-processing step obtains precision, and the exudates are a refined target area. The visual representation displayed for FPN with the EfficientNet-B0 encoder was demonstrated and shown in Figure 1.

After the removal of the optical disc, the second step involves detecting and segmenting the exudate in the image. Here, the FPN with an EfficientNet-B0 encoder is highly useful. The FPN processes multi-scale feature representation that is useful for detecting exudates with varying size and shape, as experienced in the retinal images.

The filtered images are then processed by the network through multiple layers, each corresponding to a significantly different scale of feature detection. This allows for the detection of both prominent and relatively subtle exudates across the surface of the retinas. During the segmentation, it then proceeds to what is called pixel-wise classification, which infers a probability for each pixel to belongingness to an exudate. In this approach, implementing a final softmax layer does so to interpret these probabilities such that a precise segmentation map is then generated. The usage of EfficientNet-B0 in combination with FPN not only helps the network to learn more complex features but, by the same token, makes the computation faster and more efficient, which is

Fig 1. Proposed FPN with EfficientNet-B0 Architecture

an essential characteristic for clinical applications that seek accurate and quick results.

2.1. FPN Architecture

Feature Pyramid Networks are a common architecture in computer vision and are highly suitable for use with medical imaging tasks, including object detection and semantic segmentation. Hence, in the case of medical imaging, such as exudate detection and segmentation for diabetic retinopathy, FPN is an optimal choice due to its ability to get multi-scale spatial hierarchies. This ability is critical when the identified entity’s size varies, as is the case with exudates. FPN is designed to improve the performance of convolutional networks by building a pyramid of feature maps at multiple levels of resolution. More concretely, the network creates a pyramid of features by fusing low-resolution, semantically strong features with high-resolution, semantically weak features through a top-down pathway and lateral connections.

Fig 2. FPN Architecture

Figure 2 represents the architecture of FPN. Each block level representation of FPN architecture is discussed as follows:

- **Input Image:** The process starts with an input image. This image is fed into the network, constituting the raw data that can be used for feature extraction.
- **Bottom-up Pathway:** The bottom-up pathway denotes the first feature extraction phase. While the image data is passed through the Convolutional layers (blue feature maps), the semantic level of the feature increases; the network becomes aware of more complex features in the image data. As mentioned above, the spatial resolution of the image decreases because of the pooling operation.

- **Feature Maps:** The layers of the network produce feature maps. That is, the image data has been subjected to various features the network has detected. The early feature maps have higher resolution but have less semantic meaning, while the deeper layers have more semantic meaning.
- **The top-down pathway:** Meanwhile, after the bottom-up pathway has processed the image to the deepest layer, the up-sampling of the deepest, semantic-rich feature map begins. This is because the purpose is to have feature maps that are both semantically meaningful yet have high resolution.
- **Lateral connections 1×1 convolution:** There are lateral connections as we want to combine the low-level features from the bottom-up pathway and the feature up-sampled from the top-level. These lateral connections are typically performed with 1x1 convolutions to make sure channel dimensions are compatible.
- **Predictions:** The network can now predict at each level of the top-down pathway. The feature maps have both semantic and spatial information and can predict objects of different scales. This multiscale classification allows the FPN to identify objects of different sizes.

FPN is successfully used by the model to find and segment even small, often irregularly shaped, exudates, as is common in diabetic retinopathy. The FPN architecture, which is multi-scale, makes the model robust against pathological features in retinal images that vary in size and appearance. Following the detection and segmentation, additional post-processing steps like thresholding and morphological operations can be used to process results further before a final evaluation is conducted.

2.2. EfficientNet-B0

The EfficientNet-B0 architecture is one of the models in the family of EfficientNet models designed to ensure an efficient network structure that can scale for image classification. B0 is the baseline model for this group, and the other models under this family from B1 to B7 are essentially scaled-up variants of B0, using a collection of scaling coefficients for the scaling of the depth, width, and resolution of the network.

Fig 3. EfficientNet-B0 architecture

- **Input:** The network receives an input image with a size of 224 x 224 pixels and 3 color channels, which is RGB.
- **Conv 3x3 Layer:** The first layer is Conv 3x3, which is a 2D Convolutional layer with a 3X3 kernel. Usually, during the first convolutions, the layer is responsible for the initial image feature extraction.
- **Mobile Inverted Bottleneck Conv (MBConv):** Essential to the implementation of EfficientNet-B0 is the MBConv blocks, an enhancement of the inverted residual blocks found in MobileNetV2. It is a series of layers that combine a 1x1 convolution in the front to increase the amount of input parameters, followed by a 3×3 depth wise convolution in its center, and a second 1x1 convolution that decreases the number of activations at the conclusion with squeeze-and-excitation optimization.
- **Squeeze-and-Excitation blocks:** The squeeze-and-excitation optimization applied within the MBConv blocks allows the network to concentrate on the most informative features. Specifically, this block enables adaptive recalibration of the channel-wise feature responses.
- **Swish Activation Function:** EfficientNet-B0 also uses the Swish activation function, which is defined as $f(x) = x * sigmoid(x)$; . Swish is a smooth, non-monotonic function that was found to generally outperform the common ReLU

activations in deep learning models.

- **Down sampling:** While going down to the MBConv blocks, the spatial dimensions, i.e., height and width, and tensor form feature maps are reduced or down sampled, whereas the depth or the number of channels is increased. It results in the processing of “features” at even higher levels but low resolutions. Consequently, the network does not have to compute such lower-level features that are computationally more expensive.
- **Output:** The final layers may contain a global average pooling and a dense layer with a ‘softmax’ activation function for classification purposes. It gives the number of classes to predict.

3 Results and Discussion

This section presents the simulation results of the exudates detection and segmentation by the Feature Pyramid Network on the EfficientNet-B0 encoder. The methodical emphasis was made on two main stages: the detection and elimination of the optic disc and the detection and segmentation of exudates. The effectiveness of the proposed system was confirmed by comparison with other deep learning models. The dataset contains 89 color images of the fundus, 84 of which contain at least mild non-proliferative symptoms of diabetic retinopathy MA, while 5 have no signs of diabetic retinopathy agreed by all evaluating experts are classified as images of the normal fundus. All images were captured using the same digital fundus camera with a 50-degree field of view; however, the imaging parameters varied. In summary, the dataset represents an optimal but not standard practical scenario for the calibration level when images are comparable and adequate to screen primary diagnostic methods for accuracy. Therefore, one can designate this dataset as calibration level 1 fundus images. The sample images of the dataset are shown in Figure 4.

Fig 4. Sample Images in the Dataset

The FPN works as the backbone of this model because it ensures the capture of features at different scales and helps in analyzing retinal imaging in detail. The EfficientNet-B0 encoder is the first filter that processes images at different resolutions based on compound scaling. Thus, essential features are extracted efficiently, distinguishing critical features about the optic disc from the surrounding retina with variations, in size, shape, and luminance. Later, features are integrated across levels and performed entirely due to the multi-level feature integration, typical FPN operator. This way, it ensures complete information about the global and local context, which can be achieved by the model having a better understanding of it. Finally, the segmentation mask of the optic disc from the retina is highly accurately obtained. The training and validation plots of the proposed model are depicted in Figure 5(a).

Fig 5. Performance Metric Graphs of the Proposed Model

Figure 5(a) indicates the training and validation loss of a machine learning model over multiple epochs. In the first epoch, both loss lines were high. Especially, the training loss is much higher than the validation loss. It signals an intense learning phase or could be taken as an alert for overfitting. Starting from the first epoch, however, both training and validation loss decrease fast and rapid improvements. With each subsequent epoch, the training and validation losses continue to decline and approach each other. The training loss displays minor oscillations around the validation loss; however, the trend is downward for both. It indicates that the model successfully generalizes and learns from the training data without overfitting. By the end of the eighth epoch, the trends stabilize, showing that convergence has been reached and the model may have reached its learning capacity with the provided data and configuration.

Figure 5(b) illustrates the mean Intersection over the Union score for both the training set and validation set during several training epochs. mIoU is a common metric for the quality of an image segmentation model. Both values start from lower points, reflecting the initial learning the model goes through to segment the images. With each epoch, mIoU rises sharply in both training and valid performances, reflecting the model’s rapid segmentation capabilities improvement. In the following pattern, multiplied through epochs 1 to 10, train mIoU further just slightly increases until the sixth volume. At the same time, while at points, validating mIoU units have minor fluctuations, they increase globally until volume six. The two score forms meet when their values are similar to about volume eight. The training point remains higher than the validation point, which was expected, as the model is designed to replicate, well, the data it was trained on. Therefore, such equilateral performance of staging points implies the correct balance between learning from training data and generalizing the test. Figure 5 (c) shows the accuracy of the training set and the validation set over multiple epochs as the machine learning model performs its training. Initially, both epochs have low initial accuracy, and this significantly improves in the first few epochs. Train accuracy has a steeper ascent than the validation accuracy and maintains a minimum value; this shows that the model has effectively captured the learning from the input training set as the performance remains high. Validation accuracy is also a measure of how the algorithm generalizes new data, and remains steady at maximum, implying that the model generalizes well and learns from the training set. It also shows that the model has learned from the training set and generalizes well to new data. The two curves run parallel to each other as the training continues; from epoch 4, one may conclude that the machine learning model is neither overfit nor underfit. The accuracy has plateaued at maximum levels, suggesting that the model has reached optimal performance with respect to the set model architecture and hyper-parameters.

Fig 6. Segmentation Results

Figure 6 shows the segmented results of the proposed model to detect and segment the optical disc in a given image. The first picture is a retinal fundus photograph that displays the retina with one or many lesions. The second, called “ground truth,” is the annotated areas of optical disc, presented as a yellow block in the middle of a purple background. The third image is the outcome of a segmentation task that was produced by a FPN model with an EfficientNet-B0 backbone classification. After successful segmentation of the optic disc, the model proceeds to the removal stage. This step is crucial since the optic disc’s high intensity can create artifacts that may mimic pathologies or mask real disease markers, as pathologies usually aggregate around the optic disc. The removal is carried out using inpainting strategies that fill the region previously occupied by the optic disc intelligently. These algorithms benefit from both contextual and textural information from adjacent sectors to generate a realistic and reliable continuation of the retinal background. The inpainting process uses the efficacy of the EfficientNet-B0 encoder’s feature-rich description, which can differentiate the retinal background’s texture from the optic disc after extensive training. The FPN, using the EfficientNet-B0 encoder, on the other hand, processed the images after the optic disc had been

removed properly to detect and segment the exudates.

Initially, these images are resized to a uniform scale, pixel values are normalized, and the contrast is enhanced such that exudates become easily distinguishable from the retinal background. FPN architecture employs the EfficientNet-B0 as the encoder. The encoder systematically processes the input images such that it extracts and downscales features to develop a rich, multi-scale feature map. The EfficientNet-B0 is ideally suited for the encoder role introduced above, as it finely balances the widening of the network, deepening, and its resolution such that it is excellent in terms of efficiency and accuracy. The feature maps from the EfficientNet-B0 encoder are fed into the FPN, which establishes a top-down structure through lateral connections. As a result, high-level semantic information from deep, coarse layers may be combined with low-level fine-grained information from shallow layers. Afterward, a feature pyramid is formed, comprising feature maps at various scales, and each generalizing a context window in an image. The context builder is invaluable for identifying exudates, which might have different sizes and shapes.

With the feature maps obtained from the FPN, the network does pixel-wise classification to determine whether every pixel is part of an exudate or the background. Typically, this classification is followed by a segmentation step in which the pixels classified as part of an exudate are grouped together, defining the lesion’s borders. The segmentation may have post-processing steps applied to it to clean up the raw output from the network. Such steps can include thresholding to remove predictions that are small and isolated, morphological operations to smoothen the borders of the lesions, and connectivity analysis to ensure that non-coherent regions are not classified as exudates.

The FPN with an EfficientNet-B0 encoder is trained on a dataset of annotated retinal images with known ground truth for exudates. The network’s performance is improved during training with back propagation, which adjusts the network’s weights to minimize a loss function quantifying the dissimilarity between its predictions and the ground truth. A separate set of retinal images is designated as a validation dataset. Such an ensemble allows studying model generalizing ability. The training graphs of the proposed model for the detection and segmentation of exudates are shown in Figure 7.

Fig 7. Performance Metric Graphs of the Proposed Segmented Model

Figure 7(a) represents the training curve of a proposed model and consists of loss values for both the training set and the validation set as a function of training epochs. Initially, the training and validation loss show a rapid rate of decrease; this means that the model is learning quickly from the data. After a few epochs, the rate of decrease of the loss becomes less and less, and around the fourth epoch, the gap between training and validation losses starts to vanish, and two curves run parallelly with negligible difference between them, which indicates that the model has achieved a convergence level.

Figure 7(b) displays the training of the proposed model in terms of the mean Intersection over Union for the training set and validation set across epochs. mIoU is a standard performance metric in segmentation tasks and accounts for the overlap between the area of the predicted object and the ground truth area. Both the training and validation scores begin from a moderate level and exhibit dramatic improvement in the first several epochs.

Figure 7(c) shows the accuracy of the proposed model on the training set and validation set through several epochs. The model starts with high accuracy, which rose rapidly, then plateaus after a few first epochs, meaning the model learned very quickly to classify the training data accurately. The accuracy of the training and validation data follows each other closely while still below but not varying too far from the accuracy of the training set. The validation accuracy almost mirrors the training accuracy, which is a good sign that the model generalizes well and is not overfitting. The high accuracy on the validation dataset shows that the model is good to go for as it is stable and can work well on unseen sets.

In Figure 8, the first image is a color photograph of the retina, reflecting the fundus details, which may involve exudates. The second image, labeled “Ground Truth,” presents annotated lesions marked in bright colors against the abstract dark background; this set of data is considered a reference for assessing the segmentation’s accuracy. The third image presented represents the output of a Feature Pyramid Network with an EfficientNet-B0 encoder. The pattern of the “Ground truth” and the FPN-EfficientNet-B0 output is the same, which implies that the model possesses better segmentation abilities. The proposed model is compared with the state-of-art-model and the corresponding results are reported in Figure 8.

(a) Segmentation results of Unet with EfficientNet-B0, (b) Segmentation results of UnetPlusPlus with EfficientNet-B0, (c) Segmentation results of MANet with EfficientNet-B0, (d) Segmentation results of Proposed model FPN with EfficientNet-B0

Fig 8. Comparison of Segmentation results for other State-of-the-art models

Compared to the traditional deep learning models, including the original U-Net, U-NetPlusPlus, and MANet based architectures, the proposed FPN with EfficientNet-B0 encoder demonstrated the highest performance metrics and achieved better segmented results. The Test Set mIoU and Test Set Pixel Accuracy are considered as performance metrics to validate the proposed model. The corresponding comparison results are reported in Table 1.

Table 1 compares the expected performance of the test set of various semantic segmentation models, where the backbone is EfficientNet-B0, and the design architecture is different. This comparison consists of Unet with EfficientNet-B0, UnetPlusPlus

Table 1. Comparison of various model results

Model Name	Test Set Pixel Accuracy	Test Set mIoU
Unet + EfficientNet-B0 ⁽¹¹⁾	0.9906	0.4953
UnetPlusPlus + EfficientNet-B0 ⁽¹²⁾	0.9858	0.4931
Manet + EfficientNet-B0	0.9915	0.5374
Deep learning Model ⁽¹³⁾	0.9754	-
ResNet50 + EfficientNetB0 ⁽¹⁴⁾	0.9850	-
Proposed FPN + EfficientNet-B0	0.9980	0.8152

with EfficientNet-B0, MANet with EfficientNet-B0, and Proposed FPN with EfficientNet-B0. Test Set Pixel Accuracy represents the percentage of the number of pixels in the test set that were accurately classified by the model. The higher value demonstrates the model's higher accuracy on a pixel-level. The pixel accuracy of Unet, UnetPlusPlus, and Manet is high, respectively above 98%, but Manet is slightly better than the former. Moreover, the Proposed FPN with EfficientNet B0 had the highest pixel accuracy of 99.80%, meaning correctly classified pixels most compared to the other models. Test Set mIoU provides the overlap measure in performance with the ground truth. A higher value of mIoU indicates better performance in the terminologies of precision and recall. Unet and UnetPlusPlus perform closely with each other with mIoU less than 50 %. Manet performs a significantly better term than those with mIoU of 53.74%, as for the proposed FPN with the EfficientNet-B0 shows a significant improvement in mIoU with 81.52%, which shows that not only it classifies the pixel accurately, but it is also effective against segmenting the relevant region in the image frame, which is closer to expertly annotated ground truth.

The proposed method with EfficientNet-B0 as an encoder based on the FPN outperformed all other state-of-the-art methods due to several advantages. The architecture of FPN helps to capture multi-scale spatial hierarchies accurately, which is imperative for detecting exudates of different sizes and shapes. The novel multi-scale feature representation makes the model able to tell these two classes (optic disc and exudates) apart resulting in fewer false positives. Second, use EfficientNet-B0 as an encoder to maintain a proper balance between network depth, width and input resolution. EfficientNet-B0 attempted to scale the compounds beside width, depth, and image resolution to achieve better training complexity while reducing optimization time on clinical datasets where reliable result is expected quickly. In addition, the accuracy of exudate detection was improved by means of integration optic disc removal as a preprocessing step. The model was able to eliminate the high-intensity optic disc, which improved the segmentation of the exudates due to the lower possibility artifacts mimicking pathological features. These final proposed techniques, when combined together achieve more pixel accuracy and mIoU scores compared to baselines like U-Net or even non-classical models such as U-Net++ or MANet.

4 Conclusion

This study has proposed a novel method by using a FPN with an EfficientNet-B0 as encoder, which yielded a new and effective method for exudate detection and segmentation of retinal images. FPN provided multi-scale feature representation, and EfficientNet-B0 realization for efficient extraction of features were two major factors that gained superior performance in contrast to state-of-the-art methods. This work stands out as it combines such state-of-the-art architectures with the preprocessing stage of optic disc removal, which helped to improve exudate detection accuracy by eliminating false positives. The experimental results have shown that the proposed model mustered a higher pixel accuracy (99.80%) and mIoU, which gave 81.52% as compared to state-of-the-art models such as U-Net, U-NetPlusPlus, MANet, ResNet etc. These high-performance metrics demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed model in pixel-wise classification and its segmentation. This research is a promising step forward, as the method developed can be improved upon and applied to other retinal diseases or medical imaging tasks. Suggested for future work, it is able to use the current model as a benchmark in order to train another one that includes different images. Furthermore, the implementation of such a technique in real clinical diagnostic systems can improve the sensitivity and specificity of DR screening, which leads to improved patient management.

References

- 1) Welikala RA, Hoppe A, Habib MM. Detection of microaneurysms in retinal images using an ensemble classifier. *Informatics Medicine Unlocked*. 2017;9:44–57. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imu.2017.05.006>, pp.44–57, 2017.
- 2) Fu D, Liu Y, Si ZZ. Hard exudate segmentation in retinal image with attention mechanism. *IET Image Processing*. 2021;15:587–597. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1049/ipr2.12007>, pp.587–597, 2021.
- 3) Mittal D, Kaur SMJ. Automated Detection and Segmentation of Exudates for the Screening of Background Retinopathy. *Journal of healthcare engineering*. 2023;12:1–12. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/4537253>, pp.1–12, 2023.

- 4) Wen J, Mateen NNM. Exudate detection for diabetic retinopathy using pretrained convolutional neural networks. *Complexity*. 2020;1:1–11. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/5801870>, pp.1-11,2020.
- 5) Chen Y, Li H, Wan BZC. EAD-net: a novel lesion segmentation method in diabetic retinopathy using neural networks. *Disease Markers*. 2021;p. 1–13. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6482665>, pp.1-13,2021.
- 6) Aruna PP, Smitha VK, Lathag G. Enhanced diabetic retinopathy detection and exudates segmentation using deep learning: A promising approach for early disease diagnosis. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*. 2024;p. 1–24. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-024-18629-7>.
- 7) Manan MA, Khan TM, Saadat A, Arsalan M, Naqvi SS. A Residual Encoder-Decoder Network for Segmentation of Retinal Image-Based Exudates in Diabetic Retinopathy Screening. *Electrical Engineering and Systems Science*. 2022. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2201.05963>.
- 8) Janakiramaiah B, Kalyani AKG. Diabetic retinopathy detection and classification using capsule networks. *Complex & Intelligent Systems*. 2023;9:2651–2664. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s40747-021-00318-9>, pp.2651-2664,2023.
- 9) Jena BKPK. A novel approach for diabetic retinopathy screening using asymmetric deep learning features. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*. 2023;25:1–16. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc7010025>, pp.1-16,2023.
- 10) Zhang GA, Fu XLAY. RMCA U-net: hard exudates segmentation for retinal fundus images. *Expert Systems with Applications*. 2023;120987. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2023.120987>,2023.
- 11) Alzamil ZS. Advancing Eye Disease Assessment through Deep Learning: A Comparative Study with Pre-Trained Models. *Technology & Applied Science Research*. 2024;14:14579–14587. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.7294>, pp.14579-14587.,2024.
- 12) Tulsani A, Kumar P, Pathan S. Automated segmentation of optic disc and optic cup for glaucoma assessment using improved UNET++ architecture. *Biocybernetics and Biomedical Engineering*. 2021;41:819–832. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbe.2021.05.011>.
- 13) Saranya P, Umamaheswari KM. Detection of exudates from retinal images for non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy detection using deep learning model. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*. 2024;83:53–73. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-023-17462-8>, pp.53-73,2024.
- 14) Shakibania H, Raoufi S, Pourafkham B, Khotanlou H, Mansoorizadeh M. Dual branch deep learning network for detection and stage grading of diabetic retinopathy. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*. 2024;93:10–61. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bspc.2024.106168>.